

Assessing the research anxiety level of psychology graduating students of St. Dominic College of Asia

Philip Cordova Cuizon, Jhoselle Tus, Mrinalini A. Landicho

Abstract

This study aimed to assess the research anxiety of graduating psychology students. A total of 40 psychology graduating students participated in the study. This study utilized the Research Anxiety Rating Scale developed and score-validated by Onwuegbuzie (2013) which has seven factors (Fear of Libraries, Fear of Writing, Fear of Statistics, Fear of Conducting Research, Fear of the Research Language, Fear of the Research Course, and Perceived Utility and Competence). Results showed that there is a high fear across aforementioned factors and sex has nothing to do with the seven factors analyzed. Also, significant correlations were established with selected factors.

Keywords: Research anxiety level; Fear; Psychology graduating students; Research Anxiety Rating Scale.

Philip Cordova Cuizon*

Psychology Department, School of Accountancy, Sciences, and Education, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

E-mail: pcuizon@sdca.edu.ph

Jhoselle Tus

Jesus Is Lord Colleges Foundation, Inc., Bocaue, Bulacan, Philippines
Graduate Studies Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

Mrinalini A. Landicho

Eulogio "Amang" Rodriguez Institute of Science and Technology, Manila, Philippines

Graduate Studies Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author

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Introduction

Research is a mandatory component for graduating students to complete the course. Research is crucial in all aspects of our lives, including healthcare, education, technology, and social policy. It is a research process focused on solving issues, increasing knowledge, and enhancing our comprehension of the world. Most students tend to formulate research topics that are very broad and struggle to refine them. Various sources provide guidance on formulating specific research inquiries (GMU Writing Center, 2018). Librarians aim to equip students with practical skills for post-college life. Those who teach undergraduates writing for college likewise prioritize developing students' writing abilities (Fister, 2021). Research can be challenging for kids since they are used to immediate rewards and may feel daunted by assignments that require time-consuming investigation. When conducting internet research, students often skim through text instead of reading it thoroughly for understanding. Thus, they are unable to determine the relevance of the source they are examining to their research topic (Passanisi & Peters, 2013). Research problems include selecting an appropriate topic, technique, participants, and data analysis (Lewthwaite & Nind, 2016).

In addition to concerns about resource quantity, there are also concerns about resource quality. Across our nation, the prevalent problem of fake news and unreliable sources is more apparent. Some of these objects are designed to intentionally deceive the reader. Students must possess the ability to process information critically and discerningly, a skill that can also be challenging for adults. This NPR survey demonstrates that students not only struggle with this task but also require assistance (Bielefield, 2019). Teachers face a challenge in dealing with kids who are accustomed to the convenience of most aspects of their lives. Not only is this a problem in research, but teachers may also perceive that pupils are inclined to quit when faced with challenging tasks. When faced with a difficult and intricate activity such as research, students are often inclined to complete it quickly in order to proceed to the next assignment (Bielefield, 2019).

Nichols (2023) stated that researchers face obstacles because of the slow and costly nature of their work. Occasionally, despite a researcher's diligent efforts to write a comprehensive research report, it remains unused. A study report is often disregarded due to a discrepancy in the expectations of stakeholders and researchers. Researchers must involve stakeholders in the research creation process to secure alignment and support. Alternatively, changes in product priorities or additional dependencies may hinder the integration of research findings into products and design. Not acting on research might diminish researchers' sense of impact on their team if their work fails to bring about changes in the product. Engaging in research from the initial stages of planning to the final publication can be quite satisfying. Nevertheless, other avoidable obstacles may arise at every phase of the research process. Although inefficiencies are unavoidable in research, being aware of typical errors can help reduce them (Schreffler & Huecker, 2023; Schwiesow, 2010).

Students who avoid research writing may do so due to time restrictions, a lack of research writing knowledge, and a fear of failing in research (Infotechlead, 2023). Czarnecka and Massaro (2020) stated that a common error in research is presenting research methodologies in a theoretical manner without relating them to a practical or applied issue. Many academics fail to provide explanations of the purpose and utility of methods or data in addressing practical questions or problems. Teaching research methods courses is considered difficult due to the continually changing nature of research technique material and the fragmented nature of methodological knowledge.

This study aimed to assess the research anxiety of graduating psychology students. It aims to determine the level of fear from seven factors according to Onwuegbuzie (2013): Fear of Libraries, Fear of Writing, Fear of Statistics, Fear of Conducting Research, Fear of the Research Language, Fear of the Research Course, and Perceived Utility and Competence. Furthermore, the hypothesis states that there is no significant difference among the seven factors of research anxiety based on the sex demographic profile.

Methods

The study utilized a descriptive-quantitative type of research. Forty (40) psychology graduating students participated in this study. They are profiled based on sex (biological). The study used the Research Anxiety Rating Scale developed and score-validated by Onwuegbuzie (2013). The scale consists of seven factors: items 3 and 14 are items that measure fear of libraries; items 1, 9, 13, 20, and 26 are items that measure fear of writing; items 2, 15, 22, and 28 are items that measure fear of statistics; items 4, 7, 21, 30, and 33 are items that measure fear of conducting research; items 5, 18, 25, 31, 36, 39, and 44 are items that measure fear of research language; items 6, 11, 16, 23, 32, 34, 37, and 41 are items that measure fear of the research course; items 8, 10, 12, 17, 19, 24, 27, 29, 35, 38, 40, 42, 43, and 45 are items that measure perceived utility and competence. Data were collated and statistically analyzed using T-tests for independent samples, one-way analysis of variance, and Pearson's r correlation coefficient.

Results

Table 1 shows the mean score for each factor for male and female respondents. For Fear of Libraries factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.43 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.03 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear". For Fear of Writing factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.34 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.24 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear". For Fear of Statistics factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.43 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.27 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear". For Fear of Conducting Research factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.46 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.36 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear". For Fear of Research Language factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.47 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.41 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear". For Fear of Research Course factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.24 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.23 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear". For Perceived Utility and Competence factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.06 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.01 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear".

Table 1. Mean Scores for Each Factor

Factor	Sex	Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Fear of Libraries	Male	2.43	Disagree	High Fear
	Female	2.03	Disagree	High Fear
Fear of Writing	Male	2.34	Disagree	High Fear
	Female	2.24	Disagree	High Fear
Fear of Statistics	Male	2.43	Disagree	High Fear
	Female	2.27	Disagree	High Fear
Fear of Conducting Research	Male	2.46	Disagree	High Fear
	Female	2.36	Disagree	High Fear
Fear of the Research Language	Male	2.47	Disagree	High Fear
	Female	2.41	Disagree	High Fear
Fear of the Research Course	Male	2.24	Disagree	High Fear
	Female	2.23	Disagree	High Fear
Perceived Utility and Competence	Male	2.06	Disagree	High Fear
	Female	2.01	Disagree	High Fear

Legend: 1.00-1.75 = Very High Fear; 1.76-2.51 = High Fear; 2.52-3.27 = Low Fear; 3.28-4.00 = Very Low Fear

For Fear of Conducting Research factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.46 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.36 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear". For Fear of Research Language factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.47 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.41 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear".

For Fear of Research Course factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.24 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.23 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear". For Perceived Utility and Competence factor, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.06 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear" while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.01 with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "High Fear".

Table 2 shows the test for significant difference per factor based on sex demographic profile. For Fear of Libraries, the computed p-value is 0.104 which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference and null hypothesis failed to reject. For Fear of Writing factor, the computed p-value is 0.562 which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference and null hypothesis failed to reject. For Fear of Statistics factor, the computed p-value is 0.234 which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference and null hypothesis failed to reject.

Table 2. Test for Significant Difference Per Factor Based on Sex Demographic Profile

Factor	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
Fear of Libraries	0.104	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
Fear of Writing	0.562	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
Fear of Statistics	0.234	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
Fear of Conducting Research	0.700	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
Fear of the Research Language	0.802	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
Fear of the Research Course	0.925	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
Perceived Utility and Competence	0.713	Not Significant	Fail to Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

For Fear of Conducting Research factor, the computed p-value is 0.700 which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference and null hypothesis failed to reject. For Fear of Research Language factor, the computed p-value is 0.802 which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference and null hypothesis failed to reject.

For Fear of Research Course factor, the computed p-value is 0.925 which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference and null hypothesis is accepted. For the Perceived Utility and Competence factor, the computed p-value is 0.713 which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference and null hypothesis failed to reject.

Table 3. Test for Correlation

Correlated Factors	r-value	Interpretation	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
1 2	.506	Moderate Correlation	0.001	Significant	Reject
1 3	0.245	Negligible Correlation	0.128	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
1 4	.325	Low Correlation	0.041	Significant	Reject
1 5	0.020	Negligible Correlation	0.904	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
1 6	.372	Low Correlation	0.018	Significant	Reject
1 7	0.263	Negligible Correlation	0.101	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
2 3	.336	Low Correlation	0.034	Significant	Reject
2 4	.378	Low Correlation	0.016	Significant	Reject
2 5	.333	Low Correlation	0.036	Significant	Reject
2 6	.317	Low Correlation	0.046	Significant	Reject
2 7	-0.021	Negligible Correlation	0.899	Not Significant	Fail to Reject

3 4	0.292	Negligible Correlation	0.067	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
3 5	0.164	Negligible Correlation	0.313	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
3 6	-0.040	Negligible Correlation	0.808	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
3 7	-0.049	Negligible Correlation	0.764	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
4 5	0.156	Negligible Correlation	0.338	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
4 6	0.063	Negligible Correlation	0.699	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
4 7	0.218	Negligible Correlation	0.177	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
5 6	.356	Low Correlation	0.024	Significant	Reject
5 7	0.173	Negligible Correlation	0.286	Not Significant	Fail to Reject
6 7	0.148	Negligible Correlation	0.364	Not Significant	Fail to Reject

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed); 1 - Fear of Libraries; 2 - Fear of Writing; 3 - Fear of Statistics; 4 - Fear of Conducting Research; 5 - Fear of the Research Language; 6 - Fear of the Research Course; 7 - Perceived Utility and Competence

The table above shows the test for correlation among factors. Based on the above table, there are correlated factors with significant findings. The Fear of Libraries factor is significantly correlated with Fear of Conducting Research and Fear of the Research Course since the computed p-value is less than .05. Hence, as Fear of Libraries increases, fear of Conducting Research and Fear of the Research Course also increase.

Similarly, Fear of Writing is significantly correlated with Fear of Statistics, Fear of Conducting Research, Fear of the Research Language, and Fear of the Research Course since the computed p-value is less than .05. Hence, as Fear of Writing increases, Fear of Conducting Research, Fear of the Research Language, and Fear of the Research Course also increase significantly. Fear of the Research Language is significantly correlated with Fear of the Research Course since the computed p-value is less than .05. This would mean that as Fear of the Research Language, Fear of the Research Course also increases significantly.

Discussion

The results of the study show that students have a high fear of libraries, writing, statistics, conducting research, the research language and course, and their perceived utilization and competence. This is crucial, especially since research is one of the course requirements of the program. There were also significant correlations between one's fear of libraries, fear of conducting research, and fear of the research course. Students who are afraid to visit the library for research will have difficulty gathering data, as well as the course of research as a requirement in the curriculum. Moreover, students who are afraid of writing research will have difficulty understanding statistics and applying them to their research.

Students who are afraid of research writing will have difficulty accomplishing research, comprehending research terms, and appreciating the course of research as one of the academic requirements. In addition to the discussion, students who are afraid of learning research concepts will have difficulty appreciating the research course itself.

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